
Technical Report

Report on realistic operational strategies and constraints for Belgian offshore energy hub

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Report editor: Dr. ir. Adedotun Agbemuko
Authors and contributors: Dr. ir. Adedotun Agbemuko

Executive summary

This report establishes the operational foundation for an Offshore Energy Hub considered within the DIRECTIONS project. It defines the reference system architecture, the operational philosophy, the control capabilities, and the key technical constraints that guide subsequent modelling, control development, and system studies.

The reference system is a four-terminal, bipolar ± 525 kV HVDC network with a dedicated metallic return (DMR), integrating offshore wind generation while remaining scalable for future DC network expansion. Rather than prescribing detailed control implementations, this document specifies the functional capabilities and operational boundaries that every proposed solution should satisfy.

A central design principle is operational flexibility. The system is required to support independent operation of converter poles wherever technically feasible, decoupled control of active and reactive power, seamless transitions between control modes, and coordinated operation across a wide range of network configurations. These capabilities are intended to maximize operational resilience while ensuring that all equipment operates within its physical limits.

The report also defines the minimum control functionality expected from each converter station, including active and reactive power control, DC voltage regulation, frequency and voltage support, fault ride-through, emergency control actions, and possible supplementary services such as oscillation damping. Operationally, particular emphasis is placed on maintaining stable operation during transitions between single-node and split-node configurations.

Together, these design principles, operational strategies, and constraints establish a consistent technical baseline for the control oriented work packages in the DIRECTIONS project. They define the envelope within which future control concepts, modelling activities, and validation studies will be developed, ensuring that subsequent research remains aligned with realistic operational practice and the intended evolution of the Belgian offshore energy hub.